

Fermat's Principle, Particles with Rest Mass and Quantum Mechanics Part II

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In Part I we noted that Fermat's least time principle was equivalent to conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant spatial variable and that this principle is contained in the dispersion relation $E=pc$ for a light which is strictly a wave relationship. We then argued that this wave relationship should somehow be extended to a particle with rest mass because such a particle may bounce off a mirror like light. To make the connection we wrote $0 = -Et + (px)x + (py)y$ for light with $r/t=c$ and constant $= -Et + (px)x + (py)y$ for a free particle with rest mass. In both cases Fermat's principle is contained and is equivalent to conservation of momentum in the x direction. The form $-Et + px$, however, suggests a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a frequency proportional to $1/E$ for both light and a free particle with rest mass. We argue in this note that the wavelength represents spatial information which may show conservation (e.g. of momentum in a particular direction). Thus the focus of Part I was to link a free particle with rest mass to the wave formalism of light.

Newtonian mechanics describes a free particle with rest mass as well as one moving in a potential without any need for a wavelength or frequency. In fact, for light $E=pc$ means $p \rightarrow \rho p$ and $c \rightarrow c/n$ where n is the index of refraction means that E remains constant. For a particle with rest mass (nonrelativistic) $E = p^2/2m + V(x)$. A change in p means one needs the potential to absorb or yield energy to keep E constant which is different from light. Given that Newtonian mechanics describes particles with rest mass one may ask: Why bother to try to link a free particle with light and Fermat's principle as done in Part I? The answer is that a free particle (with rest mass) diffracts or shows interference just like light in experiments. Furthermore $-Et + px$ which suggests a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and frequency proportional to $1/E$ is equivalent to the free particle action: $-m_0 \int \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ (relativistic) and $-\frac{1}{2} m_0 \int v^2$ (nonrelativistic) with $v=x/t$. Thus if Lagrangian/Hamiltonian formalism is identical to Newtonian mechanics we argue that the idea of wavelength and frequency is already present. It is not manifest because one deals with averages in $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$.

To see how wavelength may be incorporated in Newtonian conservation of energy, consider a free particle in a potential i.e. $E = p^2/2m + V(x)$. Next consider knocking out the particle so it has constant momentum. We argue that such a particle should exhibit wave-like behaviour i.e. be described in a manner linking it with light/Fermat's principle e.g. be described by $\exp(ipx)$. Fermat's principle already suggests that $d/dx \rightarrow p$ so $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction. We then argue that if $\exp(ipx)$ describes the particle when it is knocked out of the bound state, this information should still exist while it is within the bound state. Thus we suggest the form: $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ as describing the particle within a bound state. On average one has Newton's conservation of energy result, but the idea that a particle may be knocked out and should behave as a wave is also present. Furthermore the various $\exp(ipx)$ interfere so the wave nature is also present in the bound state.

Fermat's Principle and Equivalent to Conservation of Momentum in the x direction

We argued in previous notes (Part I and references) that Fermat's principle $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ where x is an invariant spatial variable is equivalent to a conservation law namely that of momentum in the x direction. Thus we argued that one could write a function which incorporates this information namely:

$$A = \text{constant} = -b t + (p_x)x + (p_y)y \quad ((1))$$

For two rays: $-b_1 dt_1/dx + p_{1x} + b_2 dt_2/dx - p_{2x} = 0 \quad ((2))$ where x is invariant spatial variable

i.e. mirrors or a medium have their surface in the x direction.

If $b_1=b_2$ then conservation of momentum in the x direction i.e. $p_{1x} = p_{2x}$ means:

$dt_1/dx - dt_2/dx = 0$ which is Fermat's principle. Note the extra minus sign is linked to the variable x appearing in t_1 and $(L-x)$ in t_2 where L is a constant i.e. the length of the mirror such that initial and final Y values have the same magnitude.

We may note that in ((1)) setting $A=0$ and $x/t=c$ leads to:

$$E=pc \quad ((3))$$

Thus we argue that using Fermat's principle alone predicts wave behaviour not only for light, but for a particle with rest mass because we argue that $A=\text{nonzero constant} = m_0 c^2$ is the constant for a particle as shown in Part I.

For the two ray situation for light or a free particle:

$$0 = (dt_1/dx - dt_2/dx) + (p_{x1} - p_{x2}) \quad \text{If } p_{x1} - p_{x2} = 0 \text{ as it does then this implies Fermat's principle.}$$

The form $-Et + px$ implies wave behaviour for both light and a free particle with a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a frequency proportional to $1/p$. This is shown experimentally. Thus these arguments are linked to conservation of momentum in a spatially invariant direction i.e. $d/dx \rightarrow p$ and wave behaviour.

Wavelength as a Spatial Counter

By linking Fermat's principle with $E=pc$ to yield $0 = -Et + (p_x)x + (p_y)y$ where x is a spatial invariant and $d/dx \rightarrow p$ (x component) it seems that the wavelength is a spatial marker of momentum and hence conservation of momentum in a particular direction. In Newtonian mechanics one might state that conservation of momentum exists in the x direction, but this is equivalent to a wavelength in this direction given by $p_x = \hbar / \text{wavelength}(x)$. The length of this x -wavelength is the same for refraction or reflection from a mirror moving at a constant v in the negative y

direction. For reflection of light from a stationary mirror the overall wavelength $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ should be the same for a given $(-x,y)$ point and (x,y) point implying that angle of incidence equals angle of reflection. Thus wavelength may act as a kind of spatial counter in problems.

Newton's Approach

Newtonian mechanics includes conservation of momentum and describes a particle's motion through $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$ where E is energy and $V(x)$ a conservative potential (and also Newton's second law). There is no presence of wavelength and no need for one to describe a particle bouncing off a mirror. One applies conservation of momentum in the x direction and conservation of energy. Nevertheless the link with Fermat's principle and waves above is interesting and furthermore the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions based on Newton's theory are equivalent to $-Et + px$ which describes a wavelength and frequency i.e.

$$\text{Action} = Lt = -m_0 t \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \text{ (relativistic) and } \text{Action} = t \cdot \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad ((4))$$

with $v = x/t$ and x and t treated as independent. Thus if Lagrangian/Action/Hamiltonian formalism is considered to be strictly equivalent to Newtonian mechanics, it seems particle-wave duality is already present in Newtonian formalism, but is not expressed in the equation of motion. $KE(x)$ is a function of x which averages or smoothes over inherent wave information as we argue in the next section.

Newtonian Formalism with Free Particle Wave Structure

If one wishes to have a free particle with rest mass exhibit wave properties then it does not suffice to describe it by $x(t)$ only. Rather $x(t)$ describes a kind of center-of-mass motion with a wave structure around it. In particular one may describe a particle by $\exp(ipx)$ if one considers x and t independent. This accounts for diffraction, two slit interference etc and is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$ with $d/dx \rightarrow p$ (x component) following from Fermat's principle.

If one knocks a bound particle from a system with a potential $V(x)$ then one expects it to be in a state $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. one has certain information. One may argue that this information should exist even in the bound equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ i.e. Newton's conservation of energy. Given that different momenta might be knocked out one may postulate:

$$KE(x) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((5a))$$

$$\text{with } W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((5b))$$

If $-i\hbar d/dx$ is a momentum operator acting on $\exp(ipx)$ then it should act in the same way on a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$. Three things are striking about ((5b)). First, given that it is a mathematical Fourier series, it may contain momenta that do not correspond to any Newtonian momentum in $\frac{p^2}{2m} + V(x) = E$. Secondly, $\exp(ipx)$ is spatially invariant because of the idea of

conservation of momentum for a free particle. This is completely different from the idea of a single $p(x)$ as in Newtonian mechanics even though ((5a)) behaves as $p(x)p(x)/2m$. Finally using ((5a)) and ((5b)) does not allow all E values as in Newtonian mechanics if one imposes boundary conditions on $W(x)$ i.e. has it become very small for large $\pm x$ values as in an oscillator problem. ((5a)) and ((5b)) are a hybrid of Newtonian conservation of energy with Fermat principle type wavelengths appearing. In fact $W(x)$ which is an average also exhibits crests and troughs, although they may have different heights and widths. The above argument is a little different from the one presented in Part I in that it centers on the $\exp(ipx)$ which constitutes $W(x)$. In Part I a form $W(x)$ was postulated with no consideration for its structure in terms of $\exp(ipx)$. One might argue that ((5b)) is a Fourier expansion, but we try to link it to physical wave behaviour.

Conclusion

In conclusion we note that Fermat's principle for light is linked to conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant spatial variable. We further argue that constant $= -Et+px$ is equivalent to Fermat's principle. If constant $=0$ one has light, if it is: $m_0c^2t_0$ (where m_0 =rest mass and t_0) one has a particle with rest mass. We argue that in both cases there is a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a frequency to $1/E$. We further note that $-Et+px$ is equivalent to the classical actions for a free particle (relativistic $-m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$) and (nonrelativistic $.5 t m_0 v^2$) if one uses $v=x/t$. Thus if Lagrangian/Hamiltonian theory is considered to be equivalent to Newtonian mechanics the idea of a wavelength and frequency is already included although it does not appear in equations of motion or in a smoothed over $KE(x)$. Thus the idea of particle wave duality present in Fermat's principle which is found in $E=pc$ (i.e $A=0= -Et+px$ with $x/t=c$) and conservation of momentum in the x direction is also found in Newtonian mechanics.

Newtonian mechanics predicts $pp/2m + V(x) = E$. If one knocks out a particle it should have a specific momentum, but also contain wave information. Thus describing it by $x(t)$ is not good enough. Rather we use $d/dx \rightarrow p$ (x component) from Fermat's principle and construct an eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$. This may be used to describe diffraction/interference. We argue that this information should also be contained in the conservation of energy equation thus $pp/2m$ which is an average should be written in terms of $\exp(ipx)$. Given that there may be different p values we suggest $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ with $KE(x) = -1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W$. This shows that if a bound particle is knocked out of its state with $V(x)$ a momentum not contained in Newton's classical range may result. It also shows that interference occurs even in a Newtonian bound state (i.e. conservation of energy) because the various $\exp(ipx)$ interfere. Finally only discrete E may be used if $W(x)$ is to have proper boundary conditions. Thus using the idea of information one may argue that if a free particle exhibits wave behaviour this should also be present in a conservation of energy equation.